

DESCRIPTION OF EXERCISES

FAIR Chemistry Data: A Research Data Management Workshop Concept

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General remarks

In this document, the exercises of the training material are explained in more detail. Each exercise description provides information on exercise type, tool, duration, learning objectives, a detailed description, as well as suggestions for alternatives or additional exercises.

All exercises are based on experiences of recent years. One resource for additional exercise is the '27 FAIR RDM exercises – A (Chemistry-specific) Catalogue' ¹, published in 2024. In the following overview, this catalogue will simply be referenced as 'NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue'.

¹ Daniela Adele Hausen et al. (2024). 27 FAIR RDM exercises – A (Chemistry-specific) Catalogue. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13353021>

Modules

This workshop concept consists of four different modules:

M01 – Basics of research data management

M02 – Documentation

M03 – Electronic laboratory notebooks

M04 – Data preservation

Exercises

Each module includes a set of exercises designed to encourage active learning and discussion. The exercises are numbered. Feel free to select the exercise that works best for you or add new exercises. The naming convention for the exercises is:

- MXXEXX
- MXX – Module number, e.g. M01, M02, M03, ...
- EXX – Exercise number, e.g. E01, E02, E03, ...

So, the first exercise in the first module is numbered as M01E01.

The exercises are primarily optimised for online workshop formats, for example by making use of collaborative tools, shared document and breakout sessions.

Alternative approaches for on-site workshops are provided for each exercise. These alternatives demonstrate how activities can be adapted for face-to-face settings through group work, printed materials and moderated discussions. Educators are encouraged to select the most suitable format for their workshop and adapt the exercises further to suit their specific context and audience.

Slides

Slides for online workshop

All the slides for the exercises have a petrol-coloured NFDI4Chem frame. The PowerPoint template contains two different exercise master slides. One is for general exercises, while the other is for exercises that use a poll tool such as Mentimeter, DirectPoll or Slido. The QR code is included in the slides using a poll tool. You can edit the link and QR code directly on the master slide, meaning you only need to update it once.

Both master slides contain a link to the workshop pad. We recommend collecting all links to exercise material, such as whiteboards (e.g. Miro) and other resources (e.g. journal articles) in a shared workshop pad (e.g. HedgeDoc) and making it available to participants. As part of the training materials, we provide a workshop pad template in Markdown format (Example_workshop_pad.md).

Slides for on-site workshop

All the slides for the exercises have a petrol-coloured NFDI4Chem frame. Unlike the online workshop slides, there is no link to the pad since it is not used in the on-site workshop.

Tools

Different tools are used in the exercises to provide an interactive experience for participants, such as whiteboards, poll tools, quizzes and pads. Below, we provide a list of tools that have proven useful to us. Not all of the solutions mentioned are free of charge, and some require registration. However, we have tried to provide free alternatives for each tool. Most universities offer at least one such solution, so check with yours.

Tools for polls and quizzes

Mentimeter (<https://www.mentimeter.com/>), DirectPoll (<https://directpoll.com/>), Slido (<https://www.slido.com/>)

Whiteboard tools

Miro (<https://miro.com/de/>), Padlet (<https://padlet.com/>), tldraw (<https://www.tldraw.com/>), Collaboard (<https://www.collaboard.app/>)

In case you are using Miro, we provided for each board an .rtp file in the 04_Example-files folder. You can import the .rtp file by selecting “+ Create new” - “Import” - “Import backup”.

Notepad

HedgeDoc (<https://hedgedoc.org/>), CryptPad (<https://cryptpad.fr/>)

Exercises for Module M01 – Basics of research data management

M01E01: Reproducibility Check

This exercise is used as an icebreaker to activate participants and encourage communication. Ask the participants to answer the question about reproducibility in their field of research.

Exercise type: Individual work, poll

Tools: Poll tool

Duration: 5 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name the probability of reproducibility in their research field.

Description: Participants are asked three questions about their perception of reproducibility in their field of research. The questions are based on the “Nature Reproducibility survey” (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.3394951.v1>). Questions:

1. How much published work in your field is reproducible?
Options: a) 0-10% b) >10-20% c) >20-30% d) >30-40% e) >40-50% f) >50-60% g) >60-70% h) >70-80% i) >80-90% j) >90-100%
2. Have you failed to reproduce someone else’s experiment?
Options: a) Yes, I failed at least once. b) No, it always worked well. c) I have not tried to reproduce someone else’s experiment yet.
3. Have you failed to reproduce your own experiment?
Options: a) Yes, I failed at least once. b) No, it always worked well. c) I have not tried to reproduce my own experiment yet.

For an example, how the preparation could look like in the software Mentimeter, check the file “M01E01_Example_Mentimeter.pdf” in the “04_Example-files” folder.

The topic of reproducibility in science is used to open the workshop. This nicely leads into the next slides, which present parts of the results of the Nature survey. Compare the participants' results with those of the actual survey.

Alternatives: If you are looking for alternative cold openers, you can try the exercises “2. Research Data Scary Tales” or “3. RDM in Chemistry – SNAFU Video” of the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue.

M01E02: Time to get to know you!

This exercise activates participants directly at the start of the workshop and provides information about their expectations.

Exercise type: Individual work, poll

Tools: Poll tool, whiteboard tool

Duration: 5 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to explain their expectations for the workshop.

Description: Participants are asked questions about their scientific background, the data they work with, as well as expectations for the workshop. Example questions:

1. In which chemical sub-discipline do you work?
Options: free text answer
2. What kind of data do you work with?
Options: free text answer
3. What are your favourite types of sweets?
Options: a) Chocolate b) Sour c) Liquorice d) Fruits
4. I would like to know more about...
Options: a) Data management planning b) Data documentation c) data publishing d) Storage and Backup e) Electronic Lab Notebook f) Legal aspects in RDM g) Other topic

For an example, how the preparation could look like in the software Mentimeter, check the file “M01E02_Example_Mentimeter.pdf” in the “04_Example-files” folder.

Make notes about the answers and refer to them later, for example when discussing data examples in the rest of the workshop. If you have discussed the topic that most participants wanted to know more about, ask them if their questions have been answered.

Alternatives: This type of poll is useful for gathering more information about participants, especially if you are running a large workshop with 20 or more participants. If you are running a smaller workshop, it is recommended that each participant answers the question directly. See also exercise “1. Introduction of Participants and their Expectations” in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue. Bear in mind that you will need to allow more time for this (1 minute per participant).

Another option is to remove question 4 from the poll and instead ask each participant to write down two topics they would like to know more about. Put the answers in a public place that can be accessed during the workshop, grouping similar topics together. During the workshop, you can refer to the topics and check the answers. This is easier to do in an on-site workshop with index cards. Online, you can use a whiteboard tool. In both cases, you will probably need a second trainer to organise the words.

M01E03: Data life cycle

Participants will become familiar with the data lifecycle and its various stages. They will understand that data management is an ongoing process, not just something that needs to be taken care of at the end.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Whiteboard, pin board, note pad, whiteboard tool, breakout rooms (online)

Duration: 25-30 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name the stages of the research data life cycle. Learners are able to associate their own activities in a research process to the stages of the research data life cycle.

Description: Prepare a whiteboard (or similar) showing the data life cycle. Participants should be divided into six small groups and assigned to a specific phase of the cycle. Each group should then discuss the following questions relating to their phase:

1. What are the tasks of the researcher?
2. Which aspects of RDM are particularly important here?
3. Which tools, software, support, ... can be used for your RDM?

For an example, how an online whiteboard could look like in the software Miro, check the file "M01E03_Example_Miro.pdf" in the "04_Example-files" folder. In case you are using Miro, you can import the file "M01E03_Import_for_Miro.rtb" which will provide you with the whiteboard shown in the PDF file.

The groups have about 10 minutes to discuss their phase and collect their ideas on the board. Afterwards the groups present their results. Other groups can then comment if they think anything is missing. They should also mention any tools or concepts that the groups may have missed. This is also a good opportunity to introduce the data management plan, electronic lab notebooks, data versioning and similar topics for the first time.

Alternatives: If your workshop is smaller, you may only want to divide participants into three groups, each of which works on two phases of the data life cycle. This exercise can also be found in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: "4. Data Life Cycle in Chemistry".

M01E04: FAIR principles quiz

The participants learn about the general ideas of the FAIR principles with the help of a quiz.

Exercise type: Individual work, quiz

Tool: Quiz, poll tool

Duration: 15 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name the FAIR principles.

Description: Participants are shown the video on the FAIR principles (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2uZxFu9SFi8>). After watching the video, participants are asked to take part in a quiz. We have prepared two versions of quiz questions. Quiz version 1 contains five questions and participants have to select the right answer. Quiz version 2 provides five statements that should be judged as true or false.

Quiz version 1:

1. What does the acronym FAIR stand for?
Options: a) Findable, Authorized, Independent, Reviewed b) Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable c) Free, Accessible, Integrated, Reliable
Correct answer: b) Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
2. To be considered Findable, data must be assigned with...
Options: a) A persistent identifier (e.g., DOI) b) An open access licence. c) A standard communication protocol (e.g., HTTP)
Correct answer: a) persistent identifier (e.g., DOI)
3. What specific element should remain accessible online, even if the data files themselves are no longer available?
Options: a) The community standard format b) API c) The metadata
Correct answer: c) The metadata
4. Answering the "w questions" (e.g., where data came from, what happened to it) helps others understand the data's:
Options: a) Standardisation process b) Usage licence c) Provenance
Correct answer: c) Provenance
5. What is a key infrastructure to enable FAIR data?
Options: a) Repository b) Funding organisation c) Publisher
Correct answer: a) Repository

Quiz version 2:

The statements are based on a published FAIR quiz (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6783901>). Statements:

1. FAIR is an acronym for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
Options: a) yes b) no c) I don't know
Correct answer: a) yes
2. FAIR is a requirement by many research funders.
Options: a) yes b) no c) I don't know
Correct answer: a) yes

3. Data must be open, to be FAIR.
Options: a) yes b) no c) I don't know
Correct answer: b) no
4. If the data are no longer available, the metadata becomes meaningless.
Options: a) yes b) no c) I don't know
Correct answer: b) no
5. Data repositories are a key infrastructure enabling FAIR data.
Options: a) yes b) no c) I don't know
Correct answer: a) yes

Mentimeter was used to develop this teaching material in the workshop. Here, you can set an option that not only selecting the right answer is important, but answering quickly is too. The person who answers the fastest gets the most points. At the end, the participant with the most points overall wins. It is recommended to restrict the time for answering to 20 seconds for quiz version 1 and 15 seconds for quiz version 2, respectively.

If your software solution does not have this option, bear in mind that the questions are quite simple, so multiple people may select the correct answers. If possible, it would be nice to provide a small reward for the top three (e.g. sweets).

For an example, how the preparation could look like in the software Mentimeter, check the file "M01E04_Example_Mentimeter.pdf" in the "04_Example-files" folder.

Alternatives: The exercise can also be found in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: "5. FAIR Principles".

M01E05: Legal framework in RDM

The legal framework can be a complex topic, so it is a good idea to start by building on what the participants already know. This exercise is useful for gauging the participants' general knowledge of legal aspects in RDM.

Exercise type: Plenary discussion, group work, collection

Tool: Not applicable

Duration: 5 – 15 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name RDM related legal areas.

Description: Participants are asked to identify the legal frameworks relevant to research data management. The central question is: 'Which legal frameworks (e.g. guidelines, laws, contracts) might play a role in RDM?' The responses are recorded on a whiteboard.

Alternatives: Alternatively, the participants can be divided into small groups to discuss the question, after which they can present the results to the plenary. If you are running an online workshop, set up breakout rooms. The exercise can also be found in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: "23. Legal Framework in RDM".

M01E06: Good Research Practice at your institution

Although every institution has implemented the DFG Good Research Practice (GRP) in a legally binding manner, the way in which this is done can vary. Participants are probably not aware of these documents, so it is a good idea to let them check their own regulations.

Exercise type: Individual work

Tool: Not applicable

Duration: 15 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to explain the relevance of research data management in relation to GRP.

Description: Give the participant two links:

1. Link to the code of conduct of the GRP (<https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/en/code-of-conduct/>)
2. Link to the GRP document of their institution

Ask the participants to compare the guidelines of the GRP code of conduct with their own institution's implementation. Ask them to focus on guidelines relevant to RDM, such as Guideline 10, Guideline 12, Guideline 13, Guideline 14 and Guideline 17.

It is important that you familiarise yourself with the institution's GRP document so that you can discuss it with the participants. This exercise is only useful if all participants are from the same institution. If you are running an on-site workshop, the participants will need to bring a laptop or similar device; otherwise, this exercise will not be feasible.

Alternatives: For on-site workshops in particular, an alternative is to present the institutional regulations and discuss any differences or similarities with the GRP.

M01E07: Who owns research data?

To make participants aware of the legal aspects of RDM, let them discuss a complex problem that could affect them in the future.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Breakout rooms (online), whiteboard

Duration: 5 – 15 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name regulations relating to copyright.

Description: Participants are divided into groups to discuss the following example:

“Rachel Researcher is working on her dissertation in Petra Professor’s research group. With the completion of her dissertation, she saves all her research data on an external hard drive, which she takes with her. However, Petra Professor would like to publish the research data in a repository that is freely accessible.”

Question:

- Who decides what happens to the data after the dissertation is completed?

For an example, how an online whiteboard could look like in the software Miro, check the file “M01E07_Example_Miro.pdf” in the “04_Example-files” folder. In case you are using Miro, you can import the file “M01E07_Import_for_Miro.rtb” which will provide you with the whiteboard shown in the PDF file.

Give participants 5–10 minutes to discuss this question in their small groups. Afterwards, they should present their results to the plenary group. The solution to this question is complex. Therefore, do not provide the answer directly. First, go through the next slides, then come back to the answer at the end of this topic.

Alternatives: To save time, you can conduct this exercise as a plenary discussion with the whole group. If you are running an on-site workshop, you could avoid forming groups by simply letting the participants discuss with their neighbours. This exercise can also be found in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: “24. Legal Aspects – Copyright”.

M01E08: Elements of a DMP

After a brief introduction to DMPs, ask the participants to brainstorm what information could be useful to include in such a document.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Whiteboard, pin board, note pad, whiteboard tool, breakout rooms (online)

Duration: 15 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name components of a data management plan.

Description: Divide the participants into groups and ask them to collect items that should be included in a DMP. They should write these down and, if possible, cluster them into categories. After 10 minutes, each group should present their results to the plenary session. Feel free to comment if you think any groups have missed something, or if you noticed anything that all groups mentioned. You can refer to the topics collected here later in the workshop.

For an example, how an online whiteboard could look like in the software Miro, check the file “M01E08_Example_Miro.pdf” in the “04_Example-files” folder. In case you are using Miro, you can import the file “M01E08_Import_for_Miro1.rtb” which will provide you with the whiteboard shown in the PDF file.

Alternatives: Another option is to let the participants write their first DMP. You can use the chemistry-specific DFG template. This exercise is described in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: “25. Creating a chemistry-specific Data Management Plan”.

Exercises for Module M02 – Documentation

M02E01: File names

Ask the participants to reflect on how they name files, and encourage them to share their typical file names.

Exercise type: Individual work, poll

Tool: Poll tool

Duration: 5 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name their naming conventions.

Description: Ask the participants to give examples of their typical file names by answering the following questions:

1. How do you name your files?
Options: free text field
2. Do you have any file naming conventions?
Options: a) Yes, I follow my own conventions. b) Yes, I follow the conventions of the project/institute. c) No, I do not follow any conventions. d) I don't know.

If you find good examples, ask the participants to explain their file names to the group. This is also a good place to mention README files as a means of documenting naming conventions.

Alternatives: This exercise is also described in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: "6. Naming Conventions".

M02E02: File naming schema

Ask the participants to reflect on how they name files, and encourage them to share their typical file names.

Exercise type: Individual work, worksheet

Tool: Not applicable

Duration: 15-20 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to develop file naming conventions under guidance.

Description: Give the participants the 'File Naming Conventions' worksheet by Kristin A. Briney (<https://doi.org/10.7907/894q-zr22>). For an online workshop, simply provide the worksheet for download. For an on-site workshop, you will probably need to print out the worksheets, or participants need to bring a laptop. Once the participants have worked through the worksheet, ask a few people to present and explain their naming convention pattern (task 7 from the worksheet).

You can find the worksheet as .docx in the “04_Example-files” folder with the name “M02E02_Worksheet.docx” or “M02E02_Worksheet.pdf”.

Alternatives: If you preferred to focus more on folder structures than file naming conventions, you can check out exercise 7, 'Naming and Structuring a Chemical Dataset', in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue. In this exercise, participants are asked to sort and organise an unstructured folder.

M02E03: Metadata v01

Participants learn what metadata is and why it is important by being shown examples of data with missing metadata.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Whiteboard, pin board, note pad, whiteboard tool, breakout rooms (online)

Duration: 25 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name different types of metadata.

Description: This exercise provides three examples of data with missing metadata. Split the participants into groups, with each group being given one example to discuss the following questions:

1. Which metadata is missing?
2. How can you categorise the metadata (e.g., administrative, technical, descriptive)?

Depending on the number of participants in your workshop, you can use three or six groups (two groups for each example of data). Alternatively, you could provide more examples of data.

The groups have 10 minutes to discuss their examples and take notes. Afterwards ask each group to present their results to the plenary.

Alternatives: This exercise is also described in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: “8. Missing Metadata in Chemistry”. The examples of data in this exercise are very chemistry specific. If you need more generic examples, check out **M02E07 Metadata v02**. Alternatively, you can check out exercise “9. Chemistry Metadata Bingo” from the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue.

M02E04: Ontologies in chemistry

Of all the topics within the field of controlled vocabularies, ontologies are probably the most complex and hardest to understand. This exercise should help participants better understand the information provided in an ontology.

Exercise type: Individual work

Tool: Computer/laptop or mobile phone

Duration: 7 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name aspects of ontologies.

Description: Provide participants with a link to the NFDI4Chem terminology service (<https://terminology.nfdi4chem.de/ts/>) and ask them to search for 'caffeine'. Participants should answer the following questions:

1. Which relationship descriptions are used?
2. What other information can you find?

They will find the entry in both the ChEBI and EFO ontologies. Allow the participants to browse for a while, then discuss their findings in the plenary session. Point out the Class Tree and the different types of information, such as synonyms, subclasses and chemical identifiers (e.g., InChI and SMILES). This is also a good opportunity to reiterate how metadata can be documented in a human- and machine-readable way using JSON.

Alternatives: If you would like the participants to explore ontologies and how they work together in more detail, look at exercise “11. Ontologies in Chemistry” of the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue.

M02E05: PubChem

During the session on chemical identifiers, the participants learnt what these are and saw some examples. They should now use this information to search a database.

Exercise type: Individual work

Tool: Computer/laptop or mobile phone

Duration: 5 - 8 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to apply persistent identifiers for searching.

Description: Give the participants a link to the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and allow them a few minutes to explore it. Ask them to answer the following guiding questions:

1. What information is provided to describe the structure of a molecule?
2. Which of these do you know and use?
3. Why are they useful?
4. Which further information can you find in PubChem?

After the participants have had time to search PubChem, discuss the questions in the plenary. During or after the discussion, show an example entry and discuss the identifiers, chemical and physical properties, classifications, and ontologies provided.

Alternatives: A similar exercise is described in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue “10. Exploring PubChem Database”.

M02E06: Process management

Participants should consider the workflows and how to document them, as well as the important metadata that needs to be recorded. One way to achieve this is to create a workflow for the research process.

Exercise type: Individual work

Tool: Piece of paper, whiteboard tool (online)

Duration: 25 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to develop simplified process flowcharts for their research.

Description: Provide participants with information on how to create a process workflow using the brewing coffee example. Make sure you explain the elements and symbols of the flow grid. After the example, the participants should create their own flow grid based on one of their research examples. Provide one working space for each participant.

It is not possible to think of everything in 15 minutes, but participants should get an idea of what writing such a flow grid involves. After 15 minutes, let 2 to 3 participants present their process to the plenary. In an online workshop, this is effortless; just show the whiteboard. In an on-site workshop, this can be tricky. For small workshops, it might hold up the workflow; for larger groups, you could take a photo with your smartphone and present it on the projector.

For an example, how an online whiteboard could look like in the software Miro, check the file "M02E06_Example_Miro.pdf" in the "04_Example-files" folder. In case you are using Miro, you can import the file "M02E06_Import_for_Miro.rtb" which will provide you with the whiteboard shown in the PDF file.

Alternatives: This exercise is also described in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: "12. Process Management".

M02E07: Metadata v02

This exercise is a variation of **M02E03: Metadata v01**, featuring more generic examples. These examples may be useful if participants in the workshop are not directly from the field of chemistry. You can also use these examples alongside the ones in M02E03 if you have more than three groups and wish to avoid two groups working on the same examples.

Exercises for Module M03 – Electronic laboratory notebooks

M03E01: 7 things an ELN should have

After a brief introduction, the participants should consider what features and functionalities an electronic lab notebook (ELN) should have to be useful for their work, before examples of different ELNs are shown. This will help you understand the participants' needs and allow you to focus on these aspects during the presentations.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Whiteboard, pin board, note pad, whiteboard tool, breakout rooms (online)

Duration: 20 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to analyse useful functionalities in an electronic lab notebook for their research.

Description: Divide the participants into groups and ask each group to list seven features that an electronic lab notebook should have to be useful for their research. For this exercise, smaller groups of up to six people can be useful. If possible, pair participants who work in similar research fields or use similar methods. After 10 minutes, each group should present their seven things/features. Take notes and refer to these features when discussing or demonstrating examples of electronic lab notebooks. Also comment on features that may not be part of an ELN (see the difference between an ELN and a LIMS). Expectation management is key when discussing ELNs.

For an example, how an online whiteboard could look like in the software Miro, check the file "M03E01_Example_Miro.pdf" in the "04_Example-files" folder. In case you are using Miro, you can import the file "M03E01_Import_for_Miro.rtb" which will provide you with the whiteboard shown in the PDF file.

Alternatives: This exercise is also described in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: "13. Electronic Lab Notebooks – 7 Features".

M03E02: Documentation template

For more generic electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs), such as eLabFTW, Labfolder and Chemotion LabIMotion, it is necessary to develop templates for experiment documentation. This exercise works well alongside the process management exercise M02E06, in which participants wrote down an entire workflow.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Note pad or a worksheet (on-site), breakout rooms (online)

Duration: 30 - 45 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to design documentation templates for their experiment under guidance.

Description: In the plenary, collect ideas for different experiments that could be described. Once you have found a few, let the participants select the one that is closest to their own research. Assign the experiment examples to working group numbers. Provide each working group with a pad containing a description of the tasks. It is useful to have a central start pad with a task description and an example, as well as links to the group pads. You can find a template for the start pad and a group pad in the material folder.

Group work can now begin. Afterwards, invite two or three groups to present their documentation templates.

You can use the “M03E02_Example_Pad.md” as template for collecting ideas and group management, and “M03E02Group_Pad.md” as template for the group work, both files are in the “04_Example-files” folder.

Alternatives: If you prefer not to work with groups, you could run this exercise individually and ask participants to select one step from the **M02E06** process management exercise and develop a template for it.

Exercises for Module M04 – Data preservation

M04E01: Data loss & storage

This exercise should increase awareness of the risks of data loss. It is also a good way to start module 04 and encourage participants to communicate with each other.

Exercise type: Individual work

Tool: Poll tool

Duration: 5 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to name causes of data loss.

Description: Participants are asked about their experience of data loss, the causes of their data loss, and how they generally store their data. The questions are:

- 1) Have you ever lost any data? If so, what was the reason for the data loss?

The options are:

1. Laptop or external hard drive was lost or stolen-
2. Hardware error
3. Malware or hacking attack
4. Software error
5. Human error (e.g. accidental deletion)
6. Bad documentation (e.g. unable to read notes or find data)
7. Other reason
8. No, I have a perfect storage and backup system.

If participants select answers other than number 8, encourage them to share their stories. You could also share your own stories or those of your colleagues.

- 2) Where do you store your data?

The options are:

1. On my laptop/personal computer
2. External hard drive or flash drive
3. My personal cloud space (e.g., Dropbox)
4. Shared drive of my working group/ institutional server
5. My personal network drive provided by my institution
6. Institutional cloud
7. Other storage option

If participants select answer 7, encourage them to share their storage option.

Alternatives: In addition to this poll, you could hand out RDM demerit badges from the Data Centre for the Humanities at the Philosophical Faculty of the University of Cologne (website: <https://dch.phil-fak.uni-koeln.de/rdm-demerit>); Zenodo publication: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14983644>). The Data Centre provides the stickers for small amounts; for larger amounts, you need to print them yourself. You can customise the badges using the published material on Zenodo and link to your own website.

M04E02: Storage media

After discussing the risk of data loss, this exercise helps participants understand how to avoid it by selecting the right storage media.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Whiteboard, pin board, note pad, whiteboard tool, breakout rooms (online)

Duration: 25 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to explain the benefits of different concepts of data storage. Learners are able to evaluate risks of data storage.

Description: Divide the participants into four groups. Each group should discuss the advantages and risks of a given storage medium. The four types of storage media are:

1. Portable devices
2. Cloud storage
3. Local storage
4. Network drives

After 10 minutes, the groups will present their results in the plenary session.

Alternatives: Not applicable

M04E03: Benefits of data publication

Ask the participants to reflect on the topic of data publication and the benefits it can bring to different communities.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: Whiteboard, pin board, note pad whiteboard tool, breakout rooms (online)

Duration: 25 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to explain the benefits of data publication

Description: In this exercise, participants will take a closer look at the following stakeholders, as well as collect reasons for not publishing research data.

1. Reasons for not publishing
2. Benefits for the public
3. Benefits for the individual researcher
4. Benefits for the research community

Participants are divided into four groups, each taking one of the stakeholders and discussing the benefits of data publication for that group for 10 minutes. After the discussion, the results are presented to the plenary.

Alternatives: This exercise is an adaptation of an exercise in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: “16. Benefits of Data Publication”. The option “1. Reasons for not publishing” was added.

M04E04: Options for publishing data

This exercise shows participants what data publication could look like and the different ways it can be done.

Exercise type: Individual work

Tool: Computer/laptop

Duration: 20 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to explain the differences between various types of data publication.

Description: For this exercise, you need to find a research paper that presents data in various ways (see this example: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-022-01278-3>). Participants should answer the following questions about the paper:

1. How do you find data?
2. Where do you find data?
3. Do you have any suggestions for improvements?

After seven minutes of independent study, discuss the answers to the questions in the plenary.

This exercise introduces multiple topics, such as data availability statements and repositories. You can refer to this example whenever you discuss these topics again.

Alternatives: In the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue, you can find multiple alternatives to this exercise: “18. Publishing Data in RADAR4Chem”, “19. Finding a chemistry-specific Repository”, “20. Chemistry Data in Generic and Chemistry-specific Repositories”, “21. Finding Chemical Data” and “22. Data Availability Statements in Chemistry”.

M04E05: Let's play taboo

Use gamification to encourage people to engage with the workshop and help them to remember what was discussed in previous workshop days/modules.

Exercise type: Group work

Tool: List of terms for taboo, breakout rooms (online), taboo cards (on-site)

Duration: 10 min

Learning objectives: Learners are able to explain the basic terms of research data management.

Description: For this exercise, you will need to compile a list of terms that were discussed in the previous workshop modules. Then, divide the participants into groups and let them play Taboo using the provided word lists. Prepare a list of 25–30 Taboo terms. Please note that you will need a moderator for each group in the breakout sessions. The moderator sends the terms to a participant as a private message. That participant must then explain the term and the other group members must guess it. For on-site workshops, prepare 25–30 cards per group. The gaming time is precisely ten minutes.

Here is a suggested list of words:

Words according to the modules

M01 - Basics of research data management

Data Life Cycle, Open Science, FAIR principles, Good Research Practice, Research Data, Copyright, Reproducible, Data Management Plan, Software Management Plan, Open Access, Open Source, Policy, Interoperability, Coffee break, RDMO, Raw Data, Funder, Secondary Data, NFDI4Chem, Open Peer Review, DFG, Licence, Creative Commons,

M02 - Documentation

Metadata, Tag, Folder Structure, Machine-readable, SMILES, InChI, Chemical Identifier, Ontology, Controlled Vocabulary, Standard, File Naming Convention, 5S Data Method, README file, Minimum Information, PubChem, Metadata Schema

M03 - Electronic laboratory notebooks

Template, eLabFTW, Chemotion ELN, Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN), ELN Finder, LabIMotion, Open Source, Access Rights, Structure Editor, Documentation

M04 - Data preservation

Publication, Repository, Persistent Identifier, Backup, Archive, Versioning, Git, EOSC, Jupyter Notebooks, DOI, ORCID, Data Availability Statement, RADAR4Chem, 3-2-1 Rule, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable, Licence, Open Access, Data Journal

Alternatives: You can also find this exercise in the NFDI4Chem exercise catalogue: “26. RDM in Chemistry – Taboo Game”, but we added some words to the word list.